

A STUDY ON SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE, AWARENESS OF CAPACITY AND HEALTH HAZARDS ON CONSUMPTION OF ALCOHOL AMONG 1ST YEAR MEDICAL STUDENTS AT SHARDA UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

Alcoholic beverages are widely consumed throughout the world and contributes one of the causes of death at global level. It is the cheapest form of drugs that are easily attainable and once get addicted to it there is no escape. The prevalence of alcohol consumption continues to rise among adolescent with the lifelong consequences in the form of depression, psychological problems, health hazards, unemployment, and incidence of road traffic accidents. In the present study we aim to understand the cause of increasing culture of consumption of alcohol among the 1st year medical students. The study was conducted on 1st year MBBS students by using a questionnaire survey. The questionnaire was formed in such a way that it gathers data from students about social acceptance, awareness of capacity and health hazards on consumption of alcohol among 1st year medical students. It was observed that 83.9% of students were nonalcoholic while 16.1% students were alcoholic. We observed in the present study that among the students consuming alcohol 29% of them started for the first time before entering medical college. Reason behind initiation is out of curiosity (62.5%) and peer pressure (15.6%). The study concluded that more than 50% of the 1st year MBBS students are non-alcoholics. The major reason for not consuming alcohol turned out to be ethics and moral values and self-control. The alcoholics tried it out of curiosity. These findings also plead for more alcohol control government guidelines as well as awareness regarding side effects and impact on longevity among the consumers.

Keywords: Alcohol, Medical Student, Peer Pressure, Questionnaire.

INTRODUCTION

Alcoholic beverages, known since Vedic period, are used for various purposes such as medicinal or worshipping and is widely consumed as a clamant. Alcohol consumption is prevalent all over the world and has been increasing rapidly throughout the world [1]. According to recent studies by The World Health Organization (WHO), the total per capita consumption of alcohol by individuals above the age of 15 years is 6.2 L, which denotes 13.5 g of pure alcohol each day. Almost 5.1% of global burden of disease is due to alcohol consumption, which is causing nearly 3.3 million deaths every year [2] Alcoholism is ubiquitous because alcohol is one of the most cheaply attainable form of drug. At first a person may consume alcohol in slight amounts only with a desire to try it, but once he or she gets addicted to it there is no escape .Even if a person is mentally strong enough to quit alcoholism, his or her body, which has been modified because of the chronic use of alcohol, won't be able to do so, so early; he or she has to overcome many obstructions put forward by the body, which in a

blanket term can be referred to as alcohol withdrawal syndrome. Hallucinations, tachycardia, seizures, vomiting, temperature elevation, headache [3]. The 12- month prevalence of AUDs in India in 2010 was 2.6% and that of alcohol dependence was 2.1%. 33.1% of road traffic accidents in the year 2012 were due to drinking and driving. The alcohol-attributable fraction (AAF) of all deaths was 5.4% in our country. Liver cirrhosis caused the death of around 62.9% of all. (4) The prevalence of alcohol consumption continues to rise among the late adolescents of age 18-20. Studies show that starting of alcoholism takes place usually in late adolescence and early adulthood, shaping one's lifestyle and causes various health hazards. Furthermore, alcoholism has become a major cause for vandalism, homicides, unemployment, depression [5]. Through the present study we can assess the social acceptance of alcoholics among 1st year medical students, which is different in different strata of society. Study also focuses on capacity of alcohol they consume and awareness among them related to the health hazards associated with it.

Aim

To understand the cause of increasing culture of consumption of alcohol among the 1st year medical students.

Objectives

1. To understand the underlying cause of consumption of alcohol in 1st year medical student.
2. To know the connection between social acceptance and alcohol consumption among 1st year medical students.
3. To know their frequency and capacity of consumption of alcohol.
4. To know the level of awareness of health hazard of alcohol consumption among 1st year medical students.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The study was conducted on **250** 1st year MBBS students of School of Medical Sciences & Research, Sharda University by using questionnaire survey. After active debate and vigorous discussion with 1st year MBBS students the questionnaire was formed in such a way so that it gathers data from students about social acceptance, awareness of capacity and health hazards on consumption of alcohol among 1st year medical students. To our survey a well-designed set of relatable Questions with answers to choose were devised on google form. Link was generated for google form and was circulated among the 1st year students. A total of 176 students participated in the study out of 250 students. The information given by the students was kept anonymized.

For our survey, question in the google form was deliberately divided into three sections. First section to identify alcoholic and nonalcoholic among the participants. Second section exclusively for alcoholics while third section was kept common questions for both alcoholic and non-alcoholic to know the general understanding of the students about social acceptance, awareness of capacity and health hazard of taking any kind of alcohol.

After getting 175 responses out of 250 students we focus on analyzing the data. Data was analyzed by spreading the results of the provided responses on excel sheet. The

inference of our survey was also depicted by charts and graphs. Graphs and charts lend credibility to our data analysis as well as enable us to correlate multiple sets of data at once.

RESULTS

The Participants of the survey were 1st year MBBS students of age group 18 - 25 years old. The first set of questionnaires were to rule out alcoholic and nonalcoholic among the participants.

The second set of questionnaires were exclusively related to students who had taken any kind of alcohol before or after joining the MBBS course. Based on their responses, we can judge the probable cause of drinking alcohol, awareness about quantity and health hazard linked with alcohol drinking.

The third set of questionnaires were framed in such a way that all the participants will be able to answer related to capacity and health hazard of taking any kind of alcohol.

Out of 250 participants only 175 students turned out for the responses. Responses received were spread on excel sheet and were analyzed with the help of charts and graphs as well.

Out of 175 students 147 (83.9%) students were nonalcoholic while 28 (16.1%) students were alcoholic.

1. Have you ever had any kind of alcohol consumption?
174 responses

2. If No, then what makes you to stay away from consuming any kind of alcohol.
146 responses

3. If Yes, then what made you to drink alcohol for the first time.

32 responses

4. When did you had your first drink

31 responses

5. How often did you drink any kind of alcohol.

27 responses

6. Is there any behavioral changes after consumption of alcohol

32 responses

7. Behavioral changes you faces after consumption of any kind of alcohol.

22 responses

8. Do you have any negative symptoms, post consumption of any kind of alcohol?

24 responses

9. Do you regret after consumption of any kind of alcohol.

31 responses

10. If Yes, then what kind of action you have taken to overcome the feeling of regret.

12 responses

11. Do you feel those who does not consume any kind of alcohol are socially unacceptable?

174 responses

12. Have you seen anyone who is not consuming any kind of alcohol and are socially unacceptable?

174 responses

13. Do you think that increase in Pub culture has provoking effect on increase consumption of any kind of alcohol?

174 responses

14. Do you think that now days Parents are more acceptable towards alcohol consumption under their supervision?

174 responses

15. Do you think that now days easy availability of alcohol in your surrounding areas has led to increase in consumption of alcohol?

174 responses

16. Do You know the Government certified age for consumption of alcohol?

174 responses

17. Do you know what amount of alcohol is adequate according to the Government guidelines of India?

174 responses

18. Do you aware of the side effects of the consumption of any kind of alcohol??

170 responses

19. Any amount and frequency of alcohol consumption will lead to one's personality deterioration.
 174 responses

20. Do you think long term alcohol consumption effects the longevity of one's life?
 174 responses

DISCUSSION

Extensive use of alcohol at an early age led to alcohol related dependence, mental depression, academic failure, health issues and behavioral changes. [6]. Use of alcohol is common among students because of its openly accessible and relatively pocket friendly for students. In one of the published Irish study 82.5% students were consumers.[7] of alcohol whereas in some study 16.6% were seen.[8]. In the present study 16.1% of students were alcoholics while 83.9% were nonalcoholic. India is the third largest market of alcoholic beverages with approximately 62.5 million alcohol consumers. The per capita alcohol consumption in India has increased by approximately 107% from 1970 to 1996 [9] It is a common belief among students that alcohol is an integral part of one's life, and that drinking is necessary to have good time. Many students drink to fit in their peer group and to look cool, which can eventually lead to heavy drinking and other hazardous effects.

Habituation and peer pressure is the factor for consuming alcohol in a study[10] while stress or tiredness is the reason in another study.[11] In another study for medical students (17–23 years), reasons for initiation of drinking included curiosity (19.6%), attending a party (17.5%), friends' influence (15.2%) and social gatherings (9.8%); and reasons for continued use included enjoyment (31.5%), as a coping mechanism for depressive symptoms (17.8%), socialization (14.8%) and to take mind off other issues (9.6%).[12]. Unlikely it was also observed in another study that student living far from family feel responsible and thus orientation towards alcohol is very less.[13] We observed in present study that among the students consuming alcohol 29% of them started for the first time before entering medical college. Reason behind initiation is out of curiosity (62.5%) and peer pressure (15.6%). Discussing the frequency of consuming alcohol among alcoholics in the present study, 51.9% consume alcohol quarterly while 40.7% 1-2 times a week while 3.2% consume daily. Alcohol

consumption becomes problematic when an individual starts drinking on a regular basis, which puts him at a high risk of severe health consequences. Report suggests that there are various patterns of drinking alcohol like social drinking, Binge drinking, Hazardous drinking pattern and alcohol dependence. In India, the practices of alcohol consumption vary across the country due to different government laws and different cultures in different states [14]. It was also found that recent studies clearly state that no amount, frequency of alcohol is good for health.[15]. Present study data shows that 43.1% students agree that any amount and frequency of alcohol consumption will lead to one's personality defect. There is a rise in the incidence of road traffic accidents under the influence of alcohol due to locomotor and cerebral dysfunction. Alcohol is a significant cause and contributing factor for domestic violence, family disharmony, and displeasure in families.[16] 44.8% of the students in our study strongly agree that alcohol consumption affects the longevity of one's life. Consumption of alcohol can cause various heart diseases and liver cirrhosis as well. Alcohol acts as neurotoxins and can damage the developing brain. Damage can be in the form of cognitive, functional, and social.[17].

It was observed that 50% of alcoholics agree to have behavioral changes after consumption of alcohol, 36.4% suffer from delusion and 27.3% face antisocial behavior while 33.3% complain of headache followed by increase craving for alcohol and nausea, vomiting. Studies shows that Social, medical, and even legal consequences are evident in alcohol consumers.[18] Medical consequences in the form of neurological, Gastrointestinal, and psychiatric problems are depicted in some studies.[19] Academic performance of an individual is also affected due to alcohol consumption.[20]. Well in our study most of the students (90.6%) were aware of side effects of the consumption of alcohol. We analyze that students (86.8%) believe that Pub-culture is the provoking factor for increased consumption of alcohol. So, consumption of alcohol depends on socio – demographical condition of that place, government guidelines of selling the alcohol and depending on number of outlets at that place.[21] Only 40.2% student know about the guidelines given by Government of India on adequate amount of alcohol intake in our study.

Data in our study shows that 80.6% of the alcoholics have no regret in consuming alcohol and those who feel regret take action to overcome by drinking nonalcoholic beverages (58.3%) followed by tracking of frequency of consuming any kind of alcohol (33.3%). There are many reasons for consuming alcohol one is the sense of belongingness and other could be imitating peers. [22]

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that more than 50% of the 1st year MBBS students are non-alcoholics. The major reason for not consuming alcohol turned out to be ethics and moral values and self-control. The alcoholics tried it out of curiosity. Half of the alcoholics found behavioral changes in themselves. Major changes were delusion and antisocial behavior, yet they do not regret consumption of alcohol. Most of the students are aware of the side effects of consumption of alcohol whereas only half of them agree that it affects the longevity of one's life. The findings from this study throw up several health challenges among adolescents on early substance use, that indirectly affect society. These findings also plead for more alcohol control government guidelines as well as awareness regarding side effects and impact on longevity among the consumers.

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